

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Transcriptome analysis reveals high tumor heterogeneity with respect to re-activation of stemness and proliferation programs

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Figure SF1: The distribution of the consensus purity estimate (CPE) values across the 19 tumors. The tumor types on the x axis are listed by in the descndng order by the mean CPE value.

Figure SF2: (A) The distribution of $\log_2(1 + CPM)$, where CPM denotes median counts per million, for the raw and CPE-corrected gene expression values. The gene expression counts were first normalized by edgeR and then corrected for tumor purity (See Methods - Correction for tumor purity). (B) A scatter plot of CPE-corrected vs. raw $\log_2(1 + CPM)$. Each point represents a gene.

Figure SF3: Higher order principal components corresponding to Figure 1. Panels (A), (B), and (C) correspond to the stemness, proliferation, and EMT-MET signatures, respectively.

Figure SF4: Clustering of tumor, normal, and ESC samples according to previously reported stemness signatures: (A) – Ben-Porath *et al* [1], (B) – Bhat-tacharya *et al* [2], (C) – Wong *et al* [3].

Figure SF5: Expression of transcriptional repressors (*CBX7*, *SALL1*) and positive regulators of stemness (*POU5F1*, *SALL4*) in tumor samples along the PC1 axis in Figure 2A. Samples were stratified into quartiles according to PC1.

Figure SF6: The positions of LUSC and LUAD tumors in the clustering diagram in Figure 2A. All tumor samples except for LUSC and LUAD are colored gray. The expression of CBX7 drops (B), and the expression of SOX2 increases (C) in tumors on the way from normal samples to iPSCs and ESCs.

Figure SF7: Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in the LUSC compared to the LUAD and the respective enrichment of their associated GO-terms.

Figure SF8: PCA clustering of tumor, normal, and ESC samples based on the controls sets of random genes that were matched by expression levels to stemness (A), proliferation (B), and EMT (C) signatures.

Figure SF9: The gradient of expression of Mesenchymal (A-D) and Epithelial (E-F) genes on the PCA clustering diagram corresponding to EMT signatures (see Figure 1C). Normal tissues are shown as gray background. Stem cells are colored as on Figure 2.

Accession	Group	Organism	n	Description
PRJNA385016	iPSC	Homo sapiens	16	Differentiation time-series (4 days, 4 replicates per day); ten passages in E8, then iDEAL feeder-free medium)
PRJNA383735	ESC	Homo sapiens	6	Different lines (H9, HUES6, MEL1); different growth conditions (E8 and KSR media);
E-MTAB-5674	ESC/PSC	Homo sapiens	30	Different lines (H9, SHEF6, HNES1); different growth conditions (tt2iLGo, tt2iLGo + iROCK, tt2iLGo feeder cell free, KSR/FGF); Fibroblast derived PSC (tt2iLGo)
E-MTAB-5114	ESC	Homo sapiens	12	hESC (H9 line); undifferentiated + differentiations (CHIR, WNT3A, BMP4)
PRJNA695233	ASC	Homo sapiens	6	Dental pulp stem cells; different age of donors (20-30 y.o., 40-50 y.o.), different growth conditions (15% serum, 60% serum)
PRJNA320078	ASC	Homo sapiens	10	Human umbilical cord blood mononuclear cell (MNC)s-derived endothelial colony forming cells (ECFC), cultured in EGM-2 BulletKit medium (Lonza) + 10% serum
PRJNA531701	ASC	Homo sapiens	8	Cardiac stem cells, inferior turbinate stem cells (ITSC); Cardiac stem cells cultured in DMEM/F-12 + 10% calf serum + FGF + EGF, ITSC cultured in DMEM/F-12 + 10% human plasma + FGF + EGF

Table ST1: The accession numbers and description of the public RNA-seq datasets that were used in the principal component analysis along with TCGA data; n denotes the (effective) dataset size.

Assay	Group	GEO	PMID	$\log_2 FC$	$\log_2 E$	Comparisons	Groups removed
Mouse GNF1M Gene Atlas	Atlas	GSE1133	15075390	0.05	3	N/A	umbilical_cord; E18 embryos; embryo day 10.5; embryo day 7.5; embryo day 9.5; embryo day 6.5; embryo day 8.5; fertilized egg; placenta; females with E18 embryos; testis; ovary; oocyte; thymus; b220+bccl; cd4+Tcell; cd8+Tcell
Mouse MOE430 Gene Atlas	Atlas	GSE10246	18442421	0.1	4.5	N/A	embryonic_stem_line.V26.2_p16; umbilical_cord; stem_cells_HSC; placenta; common_myeloid_progenitor; C2C12; C3H/10T1/2; 3T3-L1; Baf3; nih_3T3; mim6; mMCD-3; RAW_264_7
EB differentiation J1	EB_diff	GSE3749	17394647	0.05	3	J1_ES_0_hr_vs_J1_EB_14d	N/A
EB differentiation R1	EB_diff	GSE2972	17394647	0.05	3	R1_ES_0h_vs_R1_EB_14d	N/A
EB differentiation V6.5	EB_diff	GSE3231	17394647	0.05	3	V6.5_ES_0h_vs_V6.5_EB_14d	N/A
Knockdowns of pp TFs	ppTF-KDs	GSE26520	23462645	0.05	3	mESC_vs_shPou5f1-mESC; mESC_vs_shNanog-mESC; mESC_vs_Esrrb-mESC; mESC_vs_shSox2-mESC; mESC_vs_shSall4-mESC	N/A

Table S12: GEO accession numbers of the datasets that were used to assemble a set of stemness signature genes. Additional information is reported in Methods (see Signature gene sets section for details). $\log_2 FC$ denotes log-fold-change threshold (Treatment vs Control); $\log_2 E$ denotes log gene expression level threshold (Treatment + Control); Comparisons denotes the list of comparisons for differential gene expression analysis.

SupplementaryDataFile 1: TCGA sample subtype annotation and Stem cluster attribution

SupplementaryDataFile 2: Table of literature sources of manually curated stemness markers

SupplementaryDataFile 3: The list of stemness, proliferation and EMT/MET signature genes

References

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